

MULTIPHYSICS MODELING OF THE THAWING AND TEMPERING PROCESS OF BEEF MEAT IN A SOLID-STATE BASED MICROWAVE CAVITY

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Abstract – This paper describes the multiphysics modeling of the thawing and tempering process of a beef meat sample in a microwave cavity fed with patch antennas and solid-state power amplifiers. It comprises a temperature range between -18°C and 20°C, where significant changes in both the dielectric and thermophysical parameters take place. Moreover, the challenge of this work is to develop a multi-frequency system, where the correct frequency is used in each moment of the process. For that purpose, a thorough study of the effect of the ISM (Industrial, Scientifical and Medical) frequency band for the Region 2 [1], 915 MHz, on the resulting temperature profile is performed. The information of the dielectric properties is obtained through the available data, and the thermophysical properties are obtained through approximative equations.

I. INTRODUCTION.

Microwave technology and food processing have a common long history. Several researchers stated that microwaves will eventually become a standard tool in the food industry [2], however, it will be necessary to adapt microwave heating equipment to new processes, rather than to adapt the food or the process to the microwave oven itself. With that in mind, and the rise in the development of solid-state power devices, seems interesting to make a different approach. During the last 2 years, new solid-state power amplifiers, with improved efficiency and performance, readily available at the marketplace have been tested for high-power applications.

Using semiconductor-based RF generators offer control perfection in terms of the properties of the RF signal: frequency, phase, power level, modulation, and timing of the electromagnetic microwave can be set and monitored for feedback at will. This is interesting for applications in food industry. Modelling of this kind of ovens, solutions and processes facilitates the development.

These developments present an opportunity to work easily with other ISM frequencies, for instance lower bands like 915 MHz (896 MHz in Europe) or 433 MHz. Eliminating the old difficulty related to the waveguide dimensions, by the implementation of TEM antennas capable to handle high power, it will be possible to improve the performance of both commercial and industrial microwave ovens.

In this paper, a solid-state based oven prototype working at 915 MHz with two coherent feeding antennas (Microbiotech S.L., Spain) is modelled for the thawing and tempering process of a meat sample (Fig 1.).

Fig 1. View of the geometry components of the model with a surface temperature plot

II. DIELECTRIC PROPERTIES

As stated by Bengtsson and Ohlsson [2], the heat generated rises with the dielectric loss of the food material. The dielectric properties of foods are affected by frequency, temperature and composition. For some of the parameters (e.g., composition in terms of certain constituents) the impact of the dielectric properties is relatively moderate. Things also depend on type of application, e.g., if phase changes are included. Different studies have shown this effect, e.g., [3] studied the effect of the frequency in an ample range, while [4] and [5] did their studies with respect to the composition. Most data of all kind of food products is already available, and the new data in most cases show good agreement with the study by Bengtsson and Ohlsson [6], considered and referenced in many books as accurate reference data.

Within the extensive data available in the literature, the study presented by Farag in [7] meets the temperature range of interest to the present project. These dielectric values are related to the following composition: 67.8% of moisture, 11.8% of fat, 17.9% of protein and a 0.8% of ash. This composition will be used afterwards for the mass and volume fractions needed in the thermophysical equations.

The relative permittivity and loss factor are obtained from that paper. These were defined in the Comsol® model in piecewise format. In Fig 2. and Fig 3., it is presented how the data is introduced in the software.

Then the complex relative permittivity is defined as one of the material properties as a temperature dependent equation (1)

$$\epsilon_{iso} = \epsilon_1(T) - \epsilon_2(T) * j \quad (1)$$

t	f(t)
255	18
258	20
263	23.2
268	32.44
270	39.63
272	49.86
274	52.9
278	50.66
283	50.23

Fig 2. Assignment of the real part of the dielectric permittivity

t	f(t)
255	6.25
258	7
263	7.78
268	12
270	14.13
272	15.55
274	17
278	16.35
283	17.83

Fig 3. Assignment of the imaginary part of the dielectric permittivity

III. THERMOPHYSICAL PROPERTIES

Regarding the thermophysical properties that define the sample behavior within temperature, a common approach is to use approximative equations, such as defined by e.g., Choi and Okos in 1986 [8], which are written for temperatures in °C in [9]. The main parameters used are the density, thermal conductivity and specific heat; while the components of the food are the water, protein, fat and ash content. All these equations are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Thermal Property Models for Food Components ($-40 \leq T \leq 150^\circ\text{C}$)

Thermal Property	Food Component	Thermal Property Model
Density, kg/m^3	Water	$\rho_w = 9.9718 \times 10^2 + 3.1439 \times 10^{-3}T - 3.7574 \times 10^{-3}T^2$
	Ice	$\rho_{ice} = 9.1689 \times 10^2 - 1.3071 \times 10^{-1}T$
	Protein	$\rho_{prot} = 1.3299 \times 10^3 - 5.1840 \times 10^{-1}T$
	Fat	$\rho_{fat} = 9.2559 \times 10^2 - 4.1757 \times 10^{-1}T$
	Ash	$\rho_{ash} = 2.4238 \times 10^3 - 2.8063 \times 10^{-1}T$
Thermal conductivity, $\text{W}/(\text{m}\cdot\text{K})$	Water	$k_w = 5.7109 \times 10^{-1} + 1.7625 \times 10^{-3}T - 6.7036 \times 10^{-6}T^2$
	Ice	$k_{ice} = 2.2196 - 6.2489 \times 10^{-3}T + 1.0154 \times 10^{-4}T^2$
	Protein	$k_{prot} = 1.7881 \times 10^{-1} + 1.1958 \times 10^{-3}T - 2.7178 \times 10^{-6}T^2$
	Fat	$k_{fat} = 1.8071 \times 10^{-1} - 2.7604 \times 10^{-4}T - 1.7749 \times 10^{-7}T^2$
	Ash	$k_{ash} = 3.2962 \times 10^{-1} + 1.4011 \times 10^{-3}T - 2.9069 \times 10^{-6}T^2$
Specific heat, $\text{kJ}/(\text{kg}\cdot\text{K})$	Water (-40 – 0°C)	$c_{wu} = 4.1289 - 5.3062 \times 10^{-3}T + 9.9516 \times 10^{-4}T^2$
	Water (0 – 150°C)	$c_{wo} = 4.1289 - 9.0864 \times 10^{-5}T + 5.4731 \times 10^{-6}T^2$
	Ice	$c_{ice} = 2.0623 + 6.0769 \times 10^{-3}T$
	Protein	$c_{prot} = 2.0082 + 1.2089 \times 10^{-3}T - 1.3129 \times 10^{-6}T^2$
	Fat	$c_{fat} = 1.9842 + 1.4733 \times 10^{-3}T - 4.8008 \times 10^{-6}T^2$
Ash	$c_{ash} = 1.0926 + 1.8896 \times 10^{-3}T - 3.6817 \times 10^{-6}T^2$	

The presented models, are combined with the mass fractions following the equations available in [10] and described in (2) – (6).

The law of addition of specific volumes allows good estimation of the density of a mixture:

$$1/\rho = \sum x_i/\rho_i \quad (2)$$

where ρ is the density of the mixture, x_i are the mass fractions of each component and ρ_i the densities of the constituents.

The thermal conductivity of multicomponent foods lies between two limiting values. The lower limit is given by a perpendicular model that assumes that the constituents are disposed in layers perpendicular to the low of heat. The law of addition of thermal resistances in series leads to the equation:

$$k_{\perp} = 1/\sum \epsilon_i/k_i \quad (3)$$

where k_{\perp} is the thermal conductivity of the food according to the series model, ϵ_i is the volume fraction of each constituent (x_i/ρ_i) and k_i are the thermal conductivities of the constituents.

The upper limit on the thermal conductivity comes from the parallel model, in which the constituents are arranged as layers parallel to the heat low:

$$k_{\parallel} = \sum \epsilon_i k_i \quad (4)$$

A mixing model combining the two limiting values is often used as an estimate of the thermal conductivity,

$$k_{mix} = gk_{\perp} + (1 - g)k_{\parallel} \quad (5)$$

where, $g = 0.5$ is used to obtain the arithmetic mean of the two models.

As the specific heat capacity is an additive property, one can use the summation formula to predict the specific heat capacity of a food with known composition:

$$c_p = \sum x_i c_{pi} \quad (6)$$

where c_p is the specific heat capacity of the mixture, the values of x_i are the mass fractions of the various constituents, and the values of c_{pi} are the specific heat capacities of the constituents.

In the case of the heat capacity, a conditional equation will be used to pick the correct specific heat of the water, whose equations are different when the temperature is under or over 0 °C.

Lastly, the amount of water will vary from frozen to liquid within the temperature increase. This change is defined by (7)

$$x_{ice} = \frac{1.105x_w}{1 + \frac{0.7138}{\ln(T_f - T + 1)}} \quad (7)$$

where x_w is the total water fraction and T_f is the freezing point temperature. In the case of the beef meat, this value is -1.76 °C.

IV. ELECTROMAGNETIC AND MULTIPHYSICS DESIGN

The electromagnetic design of the oven, on a first approach, consists of an air box with a definition of impedance boundary condition in every outer face, emulating the behavior of an air-filled metal cavity. The patch antennas tuned at 915 MHz and fed by coaxial cables serve as the two ports. These two ports are configured with 500 W output power, and the phase can be changed parametrically. The separation and rotation between the antennas are set to have the minimum mutual coupling effect.

As can be seen in Fig 1., for instance, a dielectric dish is located at the bottom of the oven, where the beef sample is placed.

To conclude the modelling preparation, a multiphysics three steps study is defined: a phase sweep, followed by a frequency domain electromagnetic study, and concluding with a time domain, heat transfer and multiphysics coupling study.

Fig 4. Example screenshot of the surface temperature of the sample after 60 seconds of heating process.

Fig 5. Example screenshot of the surface temperature of the sample after 180 seconds of heating process.

The phase change will show how homogeneity can be achieved by changing constantly the fields. In order to have a coherent phase sweep, the frequency must be the same for both antennas. So, a frequency sweep is performed to define the optimal frequency for both antennas, with the objective of reduce both mutual coupling and self-reflection, giving as a result frequency 910 MHz.

The main part of the study, the time dependent, is used to evaluate the effect of the microwave energy source in the sample. In Fig 4. and Fig 5. can be seen the different temperature patterns in the sample after two different periods of time. And in Fig 6., a graph of the average and maximum temperature in the load volume.

V. FUTURE STEPS

As introduced at the beginning of the paper, one of the future steps will be to perform a multifrequency study. This is not as simple as it sounds, because is not an implemented feature in Comsol. Future processes will include two or three frequencies working simultaneously or in times, depending on the kind of food, the objective of the process or the desired food finished by the consumer.

Fig 5. Volume temperature change during 120s of microwave heating.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The model presented in the paper could be used to predict the heating profile and fine-tune the settings with the aim to achieve a more levelled out heating distribution. This capacity is useful, for example, for precooked food companies to understand and adapt their recipes in an efficient way, i.e., without the need of destroying a high amount of food during the process.

Being able to visualize the temperature pattern inside of a meat sample during the thawing and tempering process is another of the key features of the model.

Fig 6. Isothermal cut with the temperature pattern.

VII. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

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the food industry, as well as other heating processes where the control is one of the main requirements.

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